

Analyzing the relationship between Urban Patterns and Land Surface Temperature using Worldview-2 and LANDSAT-ETM+.

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Received: December 10, 2011 / Accepted: January 19, 2012 / Published: February 20, 2012.

Abstract: Global climate destabilization as a result of the increased urbanization is one of today's most urgent issues. The detected Urban Heat Island phenomenon in urbanized areas, combined with the decreased vegetation and the anthropogenic heat discharge, is an example of this climate change and in order to take proper actions to reduce this effect, the urban environmental analysis is more than necessary. This paper aims at analyzing and exploring the relationship between land uses of a densely populated urban area with the Land Surface Temperature (LST) combining Worldview-2 and LANDSAT ETM+ Satellite Imagery. The available thermal band of the LANDSAT image is used to extract surface temperatures of the study area on a hot summer day. Continuously, the high resolution satellite image of Worldview-2 is used for extracting the land uses. Zonal statistics were applied highlighting the zones with high and low average temperatures. Additional statistical tests (correlation analysis, analysis of variance-ANOVA etc.) were applied, for evaluating the interaction between the temperature results with the land use types.

Key words: *Land use, Land Surface Temperature, WorldView-2, Urban Heat Island, Statistical Analysis.*

1. Introduction

Global climate destabilization as a result of the increased urbanization is one of today's most urgent issues. The detected Urban Heat Island (UHI) phenomenon in urbanized areas, combined with the decreased vegetation and the anthropogenic heat discharge, is an example of this climate change.

The UHI phenomenon refers to the notion that urban areas are warmer than surrounding areas; this temperature difference usually is larger at night than during the day, and is most apparent when winds are

weak. There are several factors that cause the Urban Heat Island effect, such as the modification of the land surface by urban development, the urban geometry of built environment (size, shape etc), and the thermal characteristics of the urban surface like the asphalt and the concrete which are materials that effectively retain heat.

Aside from the effect on temperature, UHI phenomenon can produce secondary effects on local meteorology, including the altering of local wind patterns, the development of clouds and fog, the humidity, and the rates of precipitation. And this is not the only side-effect; many scientists recently report that the health and welfare of urban residents can be directly influenced by the UHI phenomenon. [1] Therefore, the UHI has gained attention of public

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administration in municipal governments, environmental protection offices and public health agencies. [2]

Since the primal cause of the UHI effect and especially for the intra-urban Heat Island, is the built environment in urban areas, the urban environmental analysis is more than necessary in order to take proper actions to reduce this effect. Taking into consideration all the above mentioned parameters, this study investigates the potential application of remote sensing and GIS for determining the growth impact to land surface temperature (LST) and Urban Heat Island (UHI) phenomenon.

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to analyze and explore the relationship between the land uses of a densely populated urban area in Greece, with the land surface temperature. More specifically, the study aims at:

- a) Extracting land uses from high resolution satellite imagery from WorldView-2, the first satellite with spectral resolution contained in eight spectral channels, using advanced image-based methodologies.
- b) Calculating Land Surface Temperature using the thermal band of LANDSAT 7 ETM+ and finally,
- c) Combining the results of the above mentioned procedures, using geospatial statistics procedures, in order to identify temperature differences between land uses and assess the correlation between land use and surface temperature.

2. Background

Several authors have explored the interaction that exists between land surface temperature and land cover/land uses using Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM+) images. In 2005 Hyung et al. [3] have used ETM+ images to extract LST for the area Kunsan city of Korea, and the statistical analysis that was developed, revealed that there is positive relationship between high built-up density and surface temperature. Mallick et al. [4], combined the derived temperature values of the ETM+ image with NDVI

values of their study area. Applying further regression analysis, and having reference temperature values from in-situ measurements, they concluded that surface temperature can be predicted correctly if the NDVI value is known.

In 2010, Hamdi [5] presented the result of a study that was carried out for the city of Uccle, in Belgium, where surface temperature values of ETM+ images were combined with urban land cover data from the database ECOCLIMAP that provides land cover information in 1km resolution. The results reveal a temperature difference of 2.3°C, between built-up and non-built-up areas of the city.

Furthermore, in 2011 Rinner and Hussain [6], used vector shapefiles of land uses for the city of Toronto Canada, for highlighting the intra- Urban Heat Island effect in the built-up area of the city. The results show that the center of the city, with less green spaces, has higher values of temperature compared to other parts of the city.

In this research, the use of ETM+ images goes one step further, by combining the LST values with the extracted features of the WorldView-2 imagery. In this case, the detailed urban environment of a densely populated area is described with automated procedures, avoiding completely the need of in-situ data. The high spatial resolution of the available WorldView-2 (0,5m) with the combination of the high spectral resolution, allows the extraction of urban features achieving high levels of accuracy. The comparison of the extracted urban features with the extracted Land Surface Temperatures for the selected area of interest constitutes the main scope of this study, analyzing the intra-Urban Heat Island effect that may be occurred.

3. Study Area and Data

High spatial resolution remotely sensed data, are the primary source for providing detailed imagery of the complex and heterogeneous urban environment. In this study, high resolution satellite imagery of

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WorldView-2 were used.

WorldView-2, launched October 2009, is the first high-resolution 8-band multispectral commercial satellite. Operating at an altitude of 770 km, WorldView-2 provides 46 cm panchromatic resolution and 1.84 m multispectral resolution. The four primary multi-spectral bands include traditional blue, green, red and near-infrared bands. The four additional bands (see fig. 1) include a shorter wavelength blue band, centered at approximately 427 nm, called the coastal band for its applications in water color studies; a yellow band centered at approximately 608 nm; a red edge band centered strategically at approximately 724 nm at the onset of the high reflectivity portion of vegetation response; and an additional, longer wavelength near infrared band, centered at approximately 949 nm, which is sensitive to atmospheric water vapor. [7]

Fig.1. Spectral Response of the WorldView 2 panchromatic and multispectral imagery. (source www.digitalglobe.com)

The available WorldView-2 images cover a part of the city of Thessaloniki in the north part of Greece. Thessaloniki, the second largest city in Greece, is a densely populated urban area characterized by a rapidly growing inhabitation and expansion. Both panchromatic and multispectral images were acquired on February, 21, 2010 and were orthorectified by DigitalGlobe. The images were provided to the authors after successful participation in the 8-band research challenge of DigitalGlobe.

The case study area covers the south east part of Thessaloniki which is municipality of Kalamaria (Fig.2). The municipality of Kalamaria was chosen as

the case study area, since it ideally includes both old and new build-up areas, with high and low built-up density respectively.

a)

b)

Fig.2. a) Study area: the Municipality of Kalamaria, North Greece, b) the WorldView-2 multispectral image of the study area

For the extraction of Land Surface Temperature, one LANDSAT 7 ETM+ image is used depicting the same area.

Landsat sensors have provided calibrated multispectral measurements of land conditions, which have proven valuable in tracking the Earth's terrestrial forests, grasslands, agricultural activity, urban growth, and surface hydrology [8], and Landsat's success is revealed in the diverse applications of the acquired information, such as extracting temperatures of the land surface.

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More specifically, the Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM+) of LANDSAT 7 acquires temperature data and stores this information as a digital number (DN) with a range between 0 and 255. Thus, with proper processing, information about LST can be extracted. In this study the available LANDSAT ETM+ image is acquired on 28th of July, and it was provided by the USGS website (www.glovis.usgs.gov). The date of this acquired image is ideal for extracting surface temperatures, since it is in the middle of summer, were the temperatures in Greece are high and the intra-Urban Heat Island phenomenon is expected to be more intense.

4. Methodology

A stratified methodology is applied in order to achieve the above mentioned objectives of this study. A brief summary of the methodology is described below:

1. Firstly high resolution satellite imagery is used for estimating and extracting the land uses of the examined area. Since both panchromatic and multispectral imagery is available, PCA techniques were applied for the pan sharpening of the imagery, obtaining a high resolution multispectral image.
2. The classification process is the next step. Both pixel-based and object-based techniques were applied in the pan-sharpened image, and finally land cover classes were extracted. Various Normalized Difference Indices were applied on the image, like NDVI, Yellow Index, Soil Index etc. for improving feature extraction techniques. Detailed information of the procedures are mentioned in [9].
3. Furthermore, the processing of the available thermal band of the LANDSAT ETM+ image is used to extract surface temperatures of the study area on a hot summer day, including: i) conversion from Digital Number to radiance, ii) conversion from radiance to brightness temperature, iii) LST retrieval.

4. Zonal statistics is applied subsequently, highlighting the zones in the study area with high and low average temperatures. Additional statistical tests (correlation analysis, analysis of variance-ANOVA) are applied, for estimating and evaluating the interaction between the temperature results with the extracted land use types.

The figure 3 shows a part of the classified WorldView-2 image. Based on the visual inspection of the image the following land-cover classes were distinguished: (1) buildings with tiled-roofs, (2) buildings with cemented-roofs, (3) buildings with bright roofs, (4) vegetation, (5) roads and (6) shadow.

Fig.3. Part of the classified image

As it was mentioned above, the land uses of the examined area were extracted after applying object oriented rule-based classification. Since the WorldView-2 image has four additional bands in the multispectral channel (coastal blue, yellow, red edge and NIR-2), this valuable information is used to constitute rules and indices for the object oriented model: a. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) which is used widely for the differentiation of vegetation and non-vegetation in urban areas, is calculated using once the NIR 1 band, and once the NIR 2 band. The second NDVI is used to set a new rule for further classifying the vegetation into low and high vegetation, since the new NIR band was found to have higher response to healthy low vegetation. [9] (fig.4).

The Yellow band is used to calculate the index:

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$$NDYG = \frac{YELLOW-GREEN}{YELLOW+GREEN} \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

This index was found to be very useful for separating the tiled roofs from the rest of the classes. For this reason, in the rule based classification a membership function is set for this class with an effective threshold of the index. (fig. 5)

Legend:

Fig.4. Application of NDVI using NDVI 2 band, for distinguishing the high and low vegetation

Legend:

Fig.5. Application of NDYG Index using yellow and green band, for distinguishing the buildings with tiled roofs.

After applying all the necessary rules and indices the desired classes are extracted. Continuously with raster

to vector shape file format transformation, all the classes are transformed to polygons, in order to be introduced in a GIS environment for further processing. With the derived polygons of the classes, *built-up density* and *urban green density* of the area of interest can be calculated. It has to be mentioned that for the built-up density only the polygons of buildings (buildings with tiled-roofs, buildings with cemented-roofs, buildings with bright roofs) were used, and the total built-up area was calculated; road networks were not within the scope of this study.

The built up density is calculated as the ratio of built up area (in m²) of the examined area with the total amount of land of the area (in m²). Respectively, the urban green density is calculated as the ratio of the observed urban green (in m²) in the area of interest with the total amount of land of the area (in m²):

$$\text{built up density} = \frac{\text{built up area}(m^2)}{\text{total amount of land}(m^2)} \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

$$\text{urban greendensity} = \frac{\text{urban green area}(m^2)}{\text{total amount of land}(m^2)} \quad (\text{eq.3})$$

These two density indicators were calculated on a non-uniform polygonal grid cell mesh based on the official neighborhood-district borders overlaid onto the study area. With this approach the spatial heterogeneity of these two parameters is expected to be more obvious.

The next figure (fig. 6) demonstrates the results of the built up density of the study area of Kalamaria. The results revealed that the examined city has high percentage of built- up area, and at the same time very low percentage of urban green. According to Grimmond and Oke [10], the urban density (of built up area of buildings only) can characterize the type of the urban settlement as of: a) *low density* urban areas when built up density has values from 0.05 to 0.2, b) *medium to high density* urban areas when built up density has values from 0.2 to 0.4 and c) *high density* when the values of built up density are higher of 0.4. The city of Kalamaria has a majority of medium to

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high built up density areas (except from three districts, with pale pink color in figure 6, which are the newly built up areas).

On the other hand, the percentages of urban green show that the green areas in the city are significantly low, even in the newly built up neighborhoods where the urban planning management is expected to have taken into consideration the needs for green space.

Fig.6. Results of the built up density in the area of Kalamaria, using the polygonal grid cell of the official neighborhood/district borders.

5. Land Surface Temperature extraction

After the extraction of land use polygons of the examined area, and the definition of urban built up density and urban green density, follows the LST retrieval using the thermal band of the Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus of Landsat 7 imagery.

The figure 7 shows the derived thematic image with Land Surface Temperatures (LST) for the area of Kalamaria, after converting the DN's for the thermal band to radiance values, and applying the inverse of the Planck function to derive temperature values. [11], [12]

Fig.7. Derived Land Surface Temperatures in Kalamaria overlaid by the district borders

The image with the temperatures reveals that the average temperature in the city of Kalamaria for the 28th of July is between 33 and 37 °C (blue and green color in the image). Furthermore, the coastal front of the city has lower temperatures than the inner part of the city, while several areas with high temperature are detected (red and dark red color in the image). Furthermore, the mean temperature values that were calculated for every district based on the derived LST, reveal that the areas that do not have coastal front, tend to have one up to three Celsius degrees higher observed temperature the same day.

Fig.8. Difference in Celsius degrees from the observed mean land surface temperature per district, in Kalamaria

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Apart from calculating mean temperature values for every district of the study area, in this study a more detailed approach is attempted by defining surface temperatures of every land use polygon that was extracted from WorldView-2 image. This is accomplished by applying zonal statistics in the environment of ArcGIS (v.10). Zonal statistics allows you to perform analysis within the zones of a vector dataset (such as polygons of a shape file dataset) based on values of a raster dataset, that depicts the same area and has the same Projection and Datum characteristics with the vector dataset. In this case, the raster used is the raster image with temperature values, derived from the LANDSAT image, and the dataset that will define the zones is the land use polygons shapefiles, extracted from WorldView-2 image.

After following the appropriate procedures, each land use polygon is associated with the corresponding LST values. The zonal statistics tools provided information about the minimum, maximum and mean observed temperature for every land use polygon. Therefore, valuable information about temperature for all land cover types in the study area is achieved. These data in parallel, constitute a large sample data suitable for further statistical analysis, since for every polygon there is information about the land use type, the min, max and mean temperature value as long as area (in m²) and allocation information.

6. Temperature differences between land-cover classes

After completing vector data analysis with zonal statistics, descriptive statistics along with an analysis of variance (ANOVA) is applied, in order to identify temperature differences between land cover classes and estimate the association between land use and surface temperature. The one-way ANOVA is conducted to verify the significance of differences between the land cover classes. The test was performed in SPSS 19, with Games-Howell post-hoc

option to test the pairwise differences in mean temperature.

Fig.8. Mean temperatures for each land cover type in Kalamaria

The ANOVA results demonstrate that the average temperatures of the road network and the buildings with cemented roofs are significantly higher than the temperatures of the other land cover types, while the lowest observed values were retrieved from the urban green land use polygons. At the same time, the ANOVA results reveal that there is no statistically significant difference in temperature values for the buildings with bright-colored roofs and tiled roofs.

7. Correlation analysis between LST, built-up density and urban green density

Since the built up and urban green density is known for the examined area, correlation analysis between LST, built up density and urban green density can be performed. This is undertaken in SPSS 19, for evaluating the impact of built up density and the urban green density at the distribution of LST in the study areas.

The results after performing Spearman's rho correlation revealed that there is positive relationship between surface temperature and built up density ($r=0.459$) suggesting that areas with high density of built-up tend to be associated with higher temperatures. On the other hand, there is a negative relation for urban green density and surface

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temperature; areas with significant urban green have lower surface temperatures. Both correlation coefficients were significant at 0.01 level.

8. Discussion/Analysis

This study examined the relationship between land cover types of an urban environment in Greece with surface temperatures on a hot summer day, and identified temperature differences between land cover types. The intra-urban patterns of UHI that were observed, confirmed that the temperatures at the inner part of the city were higher compared to the coastal front. Additionally, the average temperatures of the road network and the buildings with cemented roofs are significantly higher than the temperatures of the other land cover types. Regarding the differences between the three types of buildings that were recognized with the classification process, the results show that the buildings with bright roofs have lower observed temperatures than the other two types (buildings with cemented and tiled roofs). These results confirm that surfaces of asphalt and concrete that have low albedo and high heat capacity, tend to worsen the thermal comfort in an urban environment.

On the other hand, comparing the surface temperatures with the density of built-up and urban green, this research revealed that areas with high density of urban green tend to have lower temperatures while areas with intense built-up are associated with high temperatures.

All these results confirmed the already known intra urban heat island effect, and the surface temperatures of the three different roof type materials highlighted the unpleasant impact of using asphalt and concrete instead of eco-friendly materials. What is remarkable however, is the fact that all these results derived from two satellite images; one high resolution multispectral image of WorldView and one LANDSTAT ETM+ 7, avoiding time consuming in-situ measurements as long as other information that could be needed in order to achieve this kind of study. The advantage of

providing information with less than one meter accuracy and the capability of retrieving images for every desirable area and for every desirable date, make the satellite imagery highly compatible with the previously used data in these studies.

9. Conclusions

All the derived results demonstrate that the various land cover types in an urban environment can affect the observed intra-urban Heat Island phenomenon. Urban planners and policy makers could take these findings into consideration and design new strategies for improving the urban environment; for example replacing the concrete roofs of buildings with coatings that have low absorption and high reflectance of solar radiance. Additionally, the implementation of green roofs is another option for improving the built-up areas in an urban environment. Finally the increase of urban green canopy and the tree planting in areas with high built-up density is more than necessary.

In conclusion, the urban environmental analysis using remote-sensing data can introduce and indicate new approaches for improving and developing strategies that targeting to a better urban environment; to a better place to live in.

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